

ENZYMES IN SNAKE-VENOM. PART III. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND CHEMICALS ON THEIR ACTIVITY.

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In two papers published previously (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 450; Ghosh and De, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 627) it has been shown that the venoms of cobra (*Naja Naja*) and of Daboa (*Vipera Russellii*) contain proteolytic enzymes, the optimum activity of which is in the neighbourhood of p_H 7.0 when casein is used as substrate and at p_H 8.0 to 8.2 when gelatin and egg-albumin are used instead of casein. It has also been shown that these venoms can oxidise hæmoglobin to methæmoglobin and can hydrolyse Witte's peptone; the optimum p_H for the latter reaction being 8.2 to 8.4. Further work on this line was carried out with the venoms of Krait (*Bungarus fasciatus*) and of *Echis carinata*. The effect of temperature and of chemicals like potassium cyanide on the activity of the proteolytic enzymes present in the venoms of cobra, Daboa, and *Echis carinata* were also investigated. The results obtained are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Venoms of Krait and of Echis carinata on Proteins.

The experimental procedure adopted was similar to that described by Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) in a previous paper. Stock solutions (5%) of gelatin, Merk's dried egg-albumin and of casein were prepared and kept in a refrigerator with a few drops of toluene as preservative.

Solutions of venoms of Krait (*Bungarus fasciatus*) and of *Echis carinata* in 0.9% NaCl were prepared and their toxicity determined by intravenous injection into pigeons weighing between 300 and 310 g. It was found that the lethal doses for pigeons, of Krait and of *Echis carinata* venom were 0.4 mg. and 0.055 mg. respectively.

The stock protein solution (20 c.c.) was taken in a conical flask and its reaction adjusted to the requisite value by adding a few drops of HCl or NaOH according to need. To this solution, 10 c.c. of buffer solution of the desired p_H were added. 10 C.c. of this buffered protein solution were placed in each of the two conical flasks. To one of the flasks, 2 c.c. of venom

solution and 8 c.c. of 0.9% NaCl solution were added. To the other, which served as control, 10 c.c. of 0.9% NaCl solution only were added. After the addition of a few drops of toluene to each of the flasks, they were stoppered and placed in a thermostat at 37°. At suitable intervals of time, 5 c.c. portions of the solution were withdrawn from each set of flasks, and added to 45 c.c. of absolute alcohol containing 0.5 c.c. of a 0.5% thymolphthalein solution in alcohol. To the flask containing the 5 c.c. control sample, 0.5 c.c. of venom solution was added just before titration. The buffer solutions used were acid potassium phthalate from p_H 2.2 to p_H 5.8, acid potassium phosphate from p_H 6.0 to 8.0 and boric acid and potassium chloride from p_H 8.2 to 10.0. The interval of time allowed for digestion after the addition of venom solution and before titration (briefly denoted as *incubation period*) was for Krait venom 14 hours and for *Echis carinata* venom 6 hours.

TABLE I.

Substrate—Egg-albumin. Venom—*Echis carinata*.

0.0366N-NaOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

p_H .	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.	p_H .	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.
5.0	3.33 c.c.	3.25 c.c.	0.08 c.c.	7.5	3.16	2.57	0.59
6.0	4.2	3.90	0.30	8.0	2.72	2.10	0.62
6.5	3.81	3.40	0.41	8.6	2.28	1.70	0.58
7.0	3.52	3.00	0.52	9.0	1.85	1.40	0.45
				9.5	1.29	1.01	0.28

TABLE II.

Substrate—Casein. Venom—*Echis carinata*.

0.0366N-NaOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

p_H .	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.	p_H .	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.
5.0	3.81 c.c.	3.60 c.c.	0.21 c.c.	7.5	3.55	2.85	0.70
6.0	5.06	4.62	0.44	8.0	2.77	2.1	0.66
6.6	4.61	4.02	0.59	8.5	2.21	1.65	0.56
7.0	4.06	3.4	0.68	9.0	1.57	1.12	0.45
				9.5	1.13	0.92	0.21

TABLE III.

Substance—Gelatin. Venom—*Echis carinata*.

0.0366N-EtOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

p_H .	Control.			p_H .	Control.		
	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.		Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.
5.0	2.08 c.c.	2.01 c.c.	0.07 c.c.	8.0	1.95	1.41	0.54
6.0	2.83	2.56	0.27	8.5	1.72	1.22	0.50
6.5	2.49	2.11	0.38	9.0	1.52	1.10	0.42
7.0	2.38	1.91	0.47	9.5	1.15	0.90	0.25
7.6	2.31	1.80	0.51				

TABLE IV.

Substrate—Casein. Venom—Krait (*Bungarus fasciatus*).

0.0452N-EtOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

p_H .	Control.		Diff.
	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	
6.0	4.81 c.c.	3.76 c.c.	1.05 c.c.
7.0	4.54	2.78	1.76
7.4	4.18	2.37	1.81
8.0	3.36	1.74	1.62
9.0	1.90	0.98	0.92

TABLE V.

Substrate—Gelatin. Venom—Krait (*Bungarus fasciatus*).

0.0452N-EtOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

p_H .	Control.		Diff.
	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	
6.0	2.48 c.c.	2.10 c.c.	0.38 c.c.
7.0	2.23	1.58	0.65
7.6	2.22	1.32	0.90
8.0	2.13	1.15	0.98
9.0	1.67	0.92	0.69

From an examination of data recorded in the Tables I—III, it appears that the optimum activity of the proteolytic enzyme in the venom of *Echis carinata* is at p_{H} 8'0—8'2, the substrates being gelatin and egg-albumin; when, however, casein is used as substrate its optimum activity is in the neighbourhood of p_{H} 7'0.

Again it will be noticed from the data in the Tables IV and V that with casein and gelatin as substrates, the optimum activity of the protease in the venom of Krait (*Bungarus fasciatus*) is also in the neighbourhood of p_{H} 7.0 and p_{H} 8'0 respectively.

Action of the Venoms of Krait and Echis carinata on Peptone.

Although it has been recorded by Launoy (*compt. rend.*, 1902, 135, 401) that the venoms of cobra and of the vipers can hydrolyse the native proteins, leading to the formation of albumose, yet it was not known until recently that these venoms can act on peptone. It has recently been shown by Ghosh and De (*loc. cit.*) that the venoms of cobra (*Naja Naja*) and *Vipera Russellii* contain enzymes which can hydrolyse Witte's peptone. In this paper the results obtained with the venoms of Krait and of *Echis carinata* are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE VI.

Substrate—Peptone. Venom—*Echis carinata*. Incubation period—6 hrs.

p_{H}	0'0366N-EtOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of solution.		Diff.
	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	
5'0	6'91	6'80 c.c.	0'11 c.c.
6'0	6'56	6'30	0'26
6'5	6'27	5'80	0'37
7'0	5'49	5'00	0'49
7'6	4'49	3'90	0'59
8'0	3'74	3'10	0'64
8'5	3'08	2'45	0'63
9'0	2'44	1'90	0'54
9'5	2'00	1'50	0'50

TABLE VII.

Substrate—Peptone. Venom—Krait. Incubation period—14 hrs.

0.045*N*-EtOH-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

p_H	Active venom + substrate.	Control.	Diff.
6.0	5.96 c. c.	5.58 c. c.	0.38
6.6	5.14	4.70	0.44
7.0	4.64	4.10	0.54
7.6	3.80	3.15	0.65
8.0	3.25	2.56	0.69
8.5	2.62	1.92	0.70
9.0	2.20	1.54	0.66

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables VI and VII that the enzyme contained in the venoms of both the snakes can hydrolyse Witte's peptone and that its optimum activity lies between p_H 8.2 and p_H 8.4.

Effect of Temperature on the Activity of the Protease in Snake-venom.

A rise in temperature affects enzyme reactions in two ways, *viz.*, (i) it increases the velocity of reaction, and (ii) it begins to destroy the enzyme at higher temperatures. As a result of these two opposing factors acting simultaneously, the velocity of an enzyme reaction will at first increase, reach a maximum and then decrease as the temperature is raised. Investigations were made to determine the temperature at which the velocity of hydrolysis, caused by the proteolytic enzymes present in the venoms of cobra, Russell's viper and *Echis carinata* is the maximum. The experimental procedure was the same as described already. The data obtained at p_H 7.6 are plotted in Fig. 1. The substrate used in these experiments was casein. The results obtained by using 1 mg. of Merck's trypsin are also recorded below for the purpose of comparison. The amount of venom used per 20 c.c. of the substrate solution was 60 mg. for cobra and Russell's viper and 10 mg. for *Echis carinata*.

TABLE VIII.
Incubation period—6 hrs.

Source of enzyme taken.	p _K .	0.0414N-KOH reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of the soln.					
		Control.	37°.	40°.	50°.	60°.	70°.
Cobra venom	5.6	3.76 c.c.	4.24 c.c.	4.32 c.c.	4.49 c.c.	4.34 c.c.	3.92 c.c.
	7.6	2.70	3.32	3.40	3.65	3.42	2.98
	8.6	1.56	1.93	1.98	2.11	2.01	1.74
Russell's viper venom	6.6	3.62	4.22	4.30	4.55	4.32	3.86
	7.6	2.64	3.29	3.38	3.65	3.40	2.96
	8.6	1.55	1.91	2.00	2.27	2.03	1.75
<i>Echis carinata</i> venom	6.6	3.54	4.08	4.17	4.42	4.19	3.76
	7.6	2.55	3.25	3.35	3.63	3.37	2.90
	8.6	1.47	1.80	1.88	2.15	1.91	1.65
Trypsin	6.6	3.51	4.16	4.29	4.63	4.25	3.81
	7.6	2.50	3.36	3.50	3.91	3.55	2.92
	8.6	1.42	2.03	2.16	2.46	2.10	2.66

It will be noticed from Fig. 1 and from the data recorded in Table VIII that the maximum activity of the protease present in the venoms of cobra, Russell's viper and *Echis carinata* is in the neighbourhood of 50°. This is also the temperature at which the rate of hydrolysis of casein by trypsin (Merck's) is the maximum.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to trypsin, *Echis carinata*, Russell's viper and cobra.

*The Effect of Poisonous Chemicals on the Activity of
the Protease in Snake-venom.*

It is a known fact that poisonous substances like KCN influence the activity of the proteolytic enzymes favourably or unfavourably, depending on the nature of the enzyme. Experiments were, therefore, carried out to determine the effect of compounds like KCN, $HgCl_2$ and H_2S on the activity of the proteolytic enzymes present in the venoms of cobra, Russell's viper, and *Echis carinata*. The results obtained at p_H 7.6 only, are recorded; the inhibition observed at p_H 6.6 and at 8.6 being of the same order of magnitude as at p_H 7.6.

TABLE IX.

Effect of Potassium Cyanide.

Incubation period - 16 hrs. p_H of the substrate - 7.6.

0.0448 N-EtOH-KOH reqd.
to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

Venom used.	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(V)
	Venom only.	Venom + KCN (0.00036M).	Venom + KCN (0.00072M).	Inhibition Diff. bet. I & II.	Inhibition Diff. bet. I & III.
Cobra	3.09 c.c.	3.07 c.c.	2.81 c.c.	0.02 c.c.	0.28 c.c.
Russell's viper	3.06	3.06	2.81	0.00	0.25
<i>Echis carinatus</i>	2.91	2.89	2.66	0.02	0.25
Trypsin	3.10	3.12	2.81	0.02	0.29

TABLE X.

Effect of Hydrogen Sulphide.

EtOH-KOH (0.0493 N) reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

Venom used.	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(V)
	Venom only.	Venom + H_2S (0.00018 M).	Venom + H_2S (0.00054 M).	Inhibition Diff. bet. I & II.	Inhibition Diff. bet. I & III.
Cobra	2.92 c.c.	2.90 c.c.	2.54 c.c.	0.02 c.c.	0.38 c.c.
Russell's viper	2.77	2.76	2.47	0.01	0.30
<i>Echis carinatus</i>	2.65	2.65	2.37	0.00	0.28
Trypsin	2.84	2.83	2.46	0.01	0.38

TABLE XI.

Effect of Mercuric Chloride.

EtOH-KOH (0.0407 N) reqd. to titrate 5 c.c. of soln.

Venom used.	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(V)
	Venom only.	Venom + HgCl ₂ (0.00065M).	Venom + HgCl ₂ (0.0013M).	Inhibition Diff. bet. I & II.	Inhibition Diff. bet. I & III.
Cobra	3.42 c.c.	3.41 c.c.	3.19 c.c.	0.01 c.c.	0.23 c.c.
Russell's viper	3.39	3.38	3.20	0.01	0.19
<i>Echis carinatus</i>	3.20	3.19	3.04	0.01	0.16
Trypsin	3.41	3.40	3.21	0.01	0.20

It will be seen from the above data that the three compounds KCN, HgCl₂ and H₂S inhibit the activity of the protease present in the venoms of the snakes mentioned already. These poisonous compounds at the concentrations at which they have been used also inhibit the action of trypsin.

S U M M A R Y.

- Using casein as substrate, the optimum activity of the protease in the venoms of *Echis carinata* and Krait is in the neighbourhood of p_H 7.0. When gelatin or egg-albumin is used instead of casein, the optimum activity of the protease lies between p_H 8.0— p_H 8.2.
- The venoms of Krait and *Echis carinata* can hydrolyse peptone and the optimum activity of the enzyme lies between p_H 8.2—8.4.
- The maximum rate of hydrolysis of casein by trypsin and by the protease present in the venoms of cobra, Russell's viper and *Echis carinata* occurs in the neighbourhood of 50°.
- Compounds like KCN, HgCl₂ and H₂S inhibit the activity of trypsin and of the protease present in the venoms of cobra, Russell's viper and *Echis carinata*.

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